

Radar Interferometry for Cultural Heritage Monitoring

¹Guido Luzi*, ²Antonio Montuori**, ²Christian Bignami**, ¹Michele Crosetto*, ²Salvatore Stramondo**

¹Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Spain

²Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV) - Centro Nazionale Terremoti (CNT), Italy

* {guido.luzi; michele.crosetto}@cttc.cat

**{antonio.montuori; christian.bignami; salvatore.stramondo}@ingv.it

Abstract

The structure vibration monitoring is an operational task, which can be effectively used to support the conservation state of Cultural and Environmental Heritages for both seismic protection and civil engineering purposes. In the framework of Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) of Cultural Heritages, Radar Interferometry has demonstrated to be a powerful tool able to provide displacement time series of vibrating structures, with a precision down to tens of microns. In this study, the capabilities of an Interferometric Real aperture Radar (RAR) are investigated for structure vibration monitoring as an alternative high-resolution methodology to integrate classical techniques for non-destructive Cultural Heritage investigations. Preliminary results have been gathered over selected sites from the Cosenza historical centre, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed approach to provide spectral properties and displacement variations of vibrating structures.

1. Introduction

The Cultural Heritage Monitoring is the science that includes research strategies, methodologies, and tools needed to enable a dynamic and sustainable Cultural Heritage surveying in response to climate change and natural hazards (e.g. flooding, earthquakes, eruptions, fires) (1). Cultural Heritages includes objects, buildings and sites with historical, architectural and/or engineering relevance, which provide the living context for resilient communities in response to multivariate changes. Research in Cultural Heritage requires a multi-disciplinary approach to improve the understanding of heritage conservation and changes through observations, monitoring and modelling activities.

In the natural sciences, many non-destructive techniques (NDT) or non-destructive evaluation (NDE) methods are available, e.g. ion beam analysis, autoradiography and optical spectroscopy, which can in principle be used for Cultural Heritage conservation analysis, modelling and safeguarding purposes. In addition to them, novel geophysical, surface and subsurface techniques have been developed and tested for a multi-depth, multi-resolution and multi-scale monitoring of Cultural Heritage, overcoming the constraints of NDT/NDE analysis and giving a global vision of observed heritages (2). Within such a

framework, proximal and remote sensing methodologies have demonstrated their effectiveness for Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) purposes, e.g. photogrammetry, 3-Dimensional (3D) laser vibrometry, microgeophysics, infrared reflectography, 3D Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TLS), Global Position System (GPS), optical satellite imagery and infrared camera (3). However, some of these techniques suffer from different constraints that limit their use for operational tasks, such as the propagation of the signal, the system calibration, the local meteorological conditions, the solar illuminations and so on. Some of these drawbacks could be overridden by using radar techniques and radar sensors, as well as their integration with other techniques, thanks to the simple propagation properties of microwaves. Among the different applications of radar sensors, Radar Interferometry has demonstrated to be a powerful tool to evaluate the type and the severity of structural damages, from both operational and scientific viewpoints. In fact an Interferometric Real Aperture Radar (RAR) can be used to obtain displacement time series of vibrating structures, as confirmed by several scientific papers of recent literature (5-7). The time profiles of observed targets can be acquired down to few milliseconds, thus providing the evaluation of both sub-millimeter range vibrations and the temporal behavior of observed structures. These powerful capabilities, together with the real-time check of the Cultural Heritage conservation status, could allow an effective SHM for risk reduction and prevention purposes.

In this study, the capabilities of an Interferometric RAR for structure vibration monitoring are investigated as an alternative high-resolution methodology to integrate classical techniques for non-destructive Cultural Heritage applications. The test sites are located in the Calabria region of the Italian Peninsula, with special attention paid to the Cultural Heritages and the Civil Infrastructures of Cosenza city centre. The used instrumentation is the IBIS-S radar system, a commercial instrument developed by IDS S.p.A. company. Preliminary results, gathered over selected sites from the Cosenza historical centre, demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach for Cultural Heritage SHM.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the theoretical principles of the RAR Interferometry are described together with the technical details of the IBIS-S radar system. In Section 3, some meaningful experiments are presented over the test case of Cosenza historical centre for SHM purposes. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 4.

2. Methodology

In this section the working principle governing RAR Interferometry and some technical details of the IBIS-S radar system are properly described.

2.1 RAR Interferometry

A Radar (RAdio Detecting And Ranging) is a well known apparatus, which measures the echo of scattering objects, surfaces and volumes (hereinafter "targets") illuminated by an electromagnetic wave internally generated and operates in the microwave region of the electromagnetic spectrum. A coherent radar is able to provide not only the amplitude of the signal reflected by the target but also its phase. The amplitude of the received signal contains information about the backscattering features of observed targets and allows retrieving the radar-target distance along the Line Of Sight (LOS) of the sensor, through the position of the peaks of a range profile (4). Thanks to the use of microwaves, the radar is able to work independently of both solar illumination and atmospheric conditions.

A coherent radar can be used as an Interferometric RAR to obtain displacement time series of targets located at different ranges (i.e. parts of the vibrating structures). In fact, RAR interferometry technique allows measuring changes in the position of an object by comparison of the reflected electromagnetic wave phases at different times, with an accuracy depending on radar system characteristics (see figure 1).

Figure 1. The Interferometric RAR principle.

Vibration displacement measurements along the LOS of the sensor can be obtained through the following equation:

$$\delta\rho = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi} \cdot \Delta\varphi \quad (1)$$

where $\delta\rho$ is the measured displacement, λ is the radar wavelength and $\Delta\varphi$ is the differential phase measured by RAR (where $\Delta\varphi = \varphi_2 - \varphi_1$ according to the figure 1). Based on this rationale and according to the radar properties, the time profiles of observed targets can be acquired down to few milliseconds, providing the evaluation of both sub-millimetre range vibrations and the temporal behaviour of observed structures.

2.2 The IBIS-S radar system

IBIS-S (namely “*Image By Interferometric Survey – S*”) is a ground-based radar system, constructed and marketed by IDS S.p.A. company, with powerful interferometric capabilities for the SHM of observed structures (5). It consists of a sensor module, a control unit (a laptop computer) and a power supply unit (see figure 2a). The sensor module is a Stepped-Frequency Continuous Wave (SF-CW) band-limited apparatus, with two horn antennas generating, transmitting and receiving the electromagnetic signals that need to be processed to compute the displacement time-histories of the investigated structure. The radar is a Ku-band sensor, which operates remotely (up to 1 Km range distance in the best measuring conditions) with a central frequency of 17.2 GHz, a maximum bandwidth of 300 MHz corresponding to a range resolution of 0.5 m (see table 1). The sensor module is mounted on a tripod that is equipped with a rotating head, thus allowing the sensor to be orientated in the desired direction. The control unit is connected to the radar sensor with an USB interface, which permits to (i) configure the acquisition parameters, (ii) store the acquired signals, (iii) process the data and (iv) view the acquisition in real time (see figure 2a). Finally, the power supply is a 12 V battery unit (see figure 2a). The system can be installed and operating in half an hour.

Based on the Interferometric RAR processing described in Section 2.1, the IBIS-S system performs a 1-Dimensional (1D) sampling of the scenario illuminated by its radar antenna. The system allows providing structural vibrating displacements with a measurement accuracy lower than 0.1 mm and a sampling frequency up to 200 Hz (see table 1).

The output provided by the IBIS-S radar system is an X-Y radar plot, which shows the radar backscattering (or echo intensity) of observed targets on the Y-axis with respect to the radar-target LOS distance on the X-axis (see figure 2b). The peaks correspond to the objects providing a good backscattering radar signal in terms of high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). This range profile is acquired every sampling time thus providing, for each resolution element of the profile (namely a radar bin), a differential phase history. The analysis of the differential phase temporal series of each selected radar bin provides displacement time series at different height of the structure. When high values of radar response are present, displacements variation can be estimated down to tens of microns.

According to the above-mentioned rationale, the IBIS-S radar system represents a very useful NDT/NDE tool, that could be investigated for both static (e.g. static testing, monitoring of deformations and displacements over time, detection of structural displacements and deformations of buildings under construction), and dynamic (e.g. measurement of structure resonance frequency, measurement of the vibration modes of structures) monitoring of Cultural Heritages and Civil Infrastructures (6).

Figure 2. IBIS-S radar system. (a) The three modules of the system, i.e. the sensor, the control PC and the power supply units. (b) Typical IBIS-S radar profile.

Table 1. Technical details of IBIS-S system

Operational Frequency	17.2 GHz (Ku-band)
Type of Radar	Interferometric RAR - SF-CW
Platform	Ground-Based (GB)
Working Distance	2–1000 m
Range Spatial Resolution	0.5 m
Measurement Accuracy	<0.1 mm
Sampling Frequency	up to 200 Hz

3. Experimental results

In this section some meaningful experimental results are described showing the Interferometric RAR capabilities of the IBIS-S radar system for the vibration monitoring of

Cultural Heritages. Two relevant test buildings, with different construction features, have been selected in the urban environment of Cosenza historical center: a railway bridge (as Civil Infrastructure test site) and the bells tower of the Sant’Agostino Church compound (as Cultural Heritage test site). Experimental results concern the vibration monitoring analysis of these selected structures, which consists in providing their spectral properties and displacement variations. The retrieval of spectral properties for each monitored heritage has been accomplished through the use of Power Spectral Density (PSD) calculated according to the Welch method (8).

3.1 The rail bridge

A rail bridge located within Cosenza city centre has been monitored during the transit of a train (see figure 3a). In detail, the IBIS-S acquisition geometry allows providing three sample bins corresponding to the observed bridge (see figure 3b).

Figure 3. A rail bridge. (a) View from the IBIS-S system. (b) View of the bridge with both acquisition geometry and radar range profile, together with selected radar bins.

Experimental results show that small vibrations of the observed structure can be clearly detected in the displacement time series provided by the Interferometric RAR processing of the IBIS-S data, when the train transit occurs (see figure 4a). During the transit, a clear signal of the vibration displacement induced by the train is experienced, which ranges from a maximum of 250 microns down to lower than 50 microns (see figure 4a). As expected from the theoretical background, this result confirms that the Interferometric RAR measurements allows effectively detecting sub-millimetre LOS displacement of the structure, when a good SNR signal level is in place. A rough estimation of the vibration frequency to the bridge has been derived from a portion of its displacement temporal behaviour (see green circle in figure 4a), showing a frequency of vibration close to 7 Hz.

Other results are provided in figure 4(b), which shows the PSD calculated applying the Welch method (8) to the displacement time series of the IBIS-S Interferometric RAR acquisitions, for the three radar bins corresponding to the observed bridge. The three spectra of the radar bins identified in figure 3(b) show a clear peak at 6.74 Hz. Due to the complexity of the scenario, to better understand the spectral properties of the observed

targets, the contribution of the tripod own vibrations should be further analysed through a more careful data acquisition.

Figure 4. Vibration monitoring analysis for the rail bridge depicted in figure 3. (a) Time transients of the LOS displacement time series corresponding to the train transits. The green circle indicates the bridge vibration following the transit of the train. (b) PSD calculated for three sample radar bins, showing a peak at 6.74 Hz.

3.2 The bells tower of Sant'Agostino Church compound

The bells tower of Sant'Agostino Church compound is an old brick wall including a set of bells of different size (see figure 5a). To test the capability of the proposed technique and then collect information on the vibration features of the structure, a 45-minutes Interferometric RAR acquisition has been carried out with the acquisition geometry provided in figure 5(a). The radar was positioned about 22 m far from the church facade.

Figure 5. The bells tower of Sant'Agostino Church Compound. (a) View of the structure from the IBIS-S system. (b) Acquisition geometry and radar range profile.

A sample of the temporal behaviour relevant to the LOS displacement of the observed target is shown in figure 5(b). In detail, the bin 14 refers to the radar response of a light pole (see figure 5a), where a large LOS displacement can be observed by artificially beating the considered target. The bins 27 and 46 refer to the radar response of the church facade and the bells tower, respectively (see figure 5a). An in depth analysis of experimental results is shown in figure 6(a), which describes the displacement time series of the facade (bin 27) and the bells tower (bin 46) of Sant'Agostino Church compound by considering the toll of the bells at noon. The displacement for the main part of the building stands within 100 microns, while the displacements for the bells tower increase up to 700 microns during the toll. Results demonstrate that the ringing of the bells negligibly affects the main structure of church facade, while noticeable vibrations correlated to the toll are clearly detectable in the tower response (see twelve main peaks in figure 6a). The influence of the bells toll is very clear by analyzing the PSD of the structure over the entire acquisition (see figure 6b). In fact, the radar bins belonging to the bells tower (bins 39, 43, 44, 46) shows a frequency pattern rich of harmonics, while the ones related to the main structure (bins 27 and 30) are almost noisy.

Figure 6. (a) LOS Displacement time series corresponding to the bell toll for the main part of the structure (bin 27) and the bell tower (bin 46). (b) PSD calculated for different radar bins associated to the main structure (bins 27 and 30) and to the bells tower (bins 39, 43, 44, 46).

Conclusions

In this study, the Interferometric RAR capabilities of the IBIS-S radar system, marketed by IDS S.p.A company, have been effectively investigated for Cultural Heritage SHM purposes as an alternative high-resolution methodology to integrate classical NDT/NDE techniques. Preliminary results, gathered over a rail bridge and the bells tower of a church heritage located in the city of Cosenza, have demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed approach for SHM purposes. As expected from the theoretical background, detailed spectral properties and very high-resolution displacement variations of vibrating structures have been clearly detected for the selected buildings. Expected outcomes for future measurements campaigns concern: (1) the discrimination between the natural frequencies of the IBIS-S radar system tripod and the vibration frequencies of the observed structures, (2) the integration of obtained results with other auxiliary data provided by model, proximal and remote sensing methodologies.

Acknowledgements

The present work is supported and funded by Ministero dell'Università, dell'Istruzione e della Ricerca (MIUR) under the research project PON01-02710 "MASSIMO"- "Monitoraggio in Area Sismica di Sistemi Monumentali".

References

- (1) A. Balkema, *Cultural Heritage Conservation and Environmental Impact Assessment by Non-Destructive Testing and Micro-Analysis*, R. Van Grieken and K. Janssens, Taylor & Francis, 2004.
- (2) European Commission, *Survey and outcomes of cultural heritage research projects supported in the context of EU environmental research programmes - From 5th to 7th Framework Programme*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxemburg, pp. 48, 2011.
- (3) F. Soldovieri, J. Dumoulin, N. Masini and E. Utsi, "Noninvasive Sensing Techniques and Geophysical Methods for Cultural Heritage and Civil Infrastructures Monitoring", *International Journal of Geophysics*, Vol.2011, pp.2, 2012.
- (4) C. Gentile and G. Bernardini, "An interferometric radar for non-contact measurement of deflections on civil engineering structures: laboratory and full-scale tests", *Structure and Infrastructure Engineering*, Vol.6, no.5, pp.521-534, 2010.,
- (5) G. Luzi, O. Monserrat, M. Crosetto, "The potential of coherent radar to support the monitoring of the health state of buildings", *Research in Non-destructive Evaluation*, Vol. 23, no.3, pp.125-145, 2012.
- (6) C. Atzeni, A. Bicci, D. Dei, M. Fratini, and M. Pieraccini, "Remote survey of the leaning tower of Pisa by interferometric sensing", *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, Vol.7, no.1, pp.185-189, Jan. 2010.
- (7) C. Gentile, A. Saisi, "Dynamic measurement on historic masonry towers by microwave remote sensing", Int. Conf. *Experimental vibration analysis for civil engineering structures*, 3-5 October 2011 Varenna, Italy, C. Gentile and F. Benedettini, Vol.2, pp.524-530, 2011.
- (8) P.D. Welch, "The use of fast Fourier transform for the estimation of power spectra: A method based on time averaging over short, modified periodograms", *IEEE Transactions on Audio and Electroacoustics*, Vol.15, no.2, pp.70-73, June 1967.